

Fixed Link sub THz Propagation Measurements Exploiting Scattering

Dr Tim Brown

Academic in RF, Antennas and Propagation

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- Fixed links in sub THz are likely line of sight (free space path loss with small scattering at long distances) or non line of sight with single reflection.
- At sub THz wavelengths there is opportunity to exploit the multipath contained within the reflecting building structure.
- This allows reflection where the incident and reflection angle are not equal.
- But also there is not a definitive theoretical point in which the reflection is best – it requires measurement.

What kind of scattering do we see on different surfaces?

Parameter	Value
Spatial range	1-230 mm
Spatial resolution	1 mm

Internal composite structure makes significant difference to the frequency selectivity

IRR Window

Pebbledash Wall

Brick Wall

Other effects from internal 'infrastructure' such as wall studs

Parameter	Value
Spatial range	1-230 mm
Spatial resolution	1 mm

Other effects from internal 'infrastructure' such as wall studs

Parameter	Value
Angular range	0° - 40°
Angular resolution	1°

Power delay profiles

Between studs

Over stud

Over wood

Polynomial form: $h = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_1^2 + \dots + a_nx_1^n$

Between studs

Over stud

Over wood

Based on the well known bistatic radar equation a path loss can be formed:

$$PL(f, \Delta\Phi) = \frac{G_1 G_2 \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^3 (d_1)^2 (d_2)^2} |\sigma_{\text{eff}}(f, \Delta\Phi)|$$

- In this model, we define an “effective” frequency selective RCS due to scattering.
- The effective RCS is going to be dependent on distances as well as Tx and Rx angles.

Power delay profiles

Relevant Publications

- D. Serghiou, M. Khalily, A. Ali, T. Brown and R. Tafazolli, “Autoregressive Modelling for Sub-THz Spatio-Temporal Wideband Scattered Reflection Coefficient Measurement of Complex Structures”, IET Microwaves, Antennas and Propagation, vol. 18, no. 7, pp 494–504, 2024, doi: 10.1049/mia2.12461.
- D. Serghiou, M. Khalily, A. Ali, T. Brown and R. Tafazolli, “Characterisation of Frequency Selective Reflections off Indoor Surfaces for 92–110 GHz,” 2022 16th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP), Madrid, Spain, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi:10.23919/EuCAP53622.2022.9769552.
- D. Serghiou, M. Khalily, A. Ali, T. Brown and R. Tafazolli, “Characterization of Effective RCS for Fixed NLoS Sub-THz Links With Single Scattered Reflections,” IEEE Open Journal of Antennas and Propagation, doi: 10.1109/OJAP.2024.3448253.